

RESEARCH PAPER

VARIATIONS IN MORPHOMETRICS AND MERISTIC TRAITS OF FINS OF *Oreochromis niloticus* AND *Tilapia zillii* FROM A DAM IN EKITI STATE, SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA

Fagbuaro Omotayo
Ekiti State University, Faculty of Science, Department of Zoology, P.M.B. 5363, Ado-Ekti,
Ekiti State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The study is conducted to compare morphology and fin rays counts of different fins of *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Tilapia zillii* from Ureje dam, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. The results revealed that there were no strong correlations between various fins lengths, fin rays and the total length of the two fish species. The results also showed that both fish species have similar fin ray numbers therefore; biochemical analysis may be required to further confirm their taxonomic characteristics and the purity of the genetic composition of the two species

KEYWORDS: Variation, Morphometric *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Tilapia zillii*, Fins, Dam, Nigeria

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Corresponding Author: omofagbuaro@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Fishes are highly important in the development of a country both economically and healthwise as source of protein with low cholesterol level in the diets of many populace as well as an intermediate host to some parasite (Imam *et al.*, 2010). The success of fishery industries depend on growth and reproductive potential of the concerned fish species. The development and improvement of growth of fish species mostly depends on the knowledge of their biology. Human beings need fish throughout the year as a source of protein to complement animal protein required for their growth and development. Cichlidae species (*Oreochromis*, *Sarotherodon* and *Tilapia*) add values to the life of fish farmers and commercial fishery of inland waters of most countries of the world. They are tolerance to a variety of habitats and omnivore nature of their feeding habit confer them an important element of fish farming which demands mode of their life and ecological requirements (Omoniyi and Agbon, 2008).

Previous studies of the *Tilapia* have focused almost entirely on its importance and suitability for aquaculture, adaptation to salt water habit and meat quality and not on morphometric analysis (Mert and Cicek, (2010), Breves *et al* (2010) and Chaijan (2011). Morphometry according to Webster, (2006) is concerned with studying variation and change in form of an organism and meristic traits count remains the simplest and most direct way among methods of species identifications. The analysis of phenotypic variations in morphometric characters or meristic counts is reported to be one of the methods most commonly used to categorize stocks of fish (Bronte *et al.*, 1999, Hockaday *et al* 2000). It has also been reported that the shapes and structures of fins and fin rays of various fish show modifications as a result of varied swimming habits, habitat sex, growth factors and mode of life of the fishes (Ugwumba and Ugwumba 1993, Weisel 1995 Tantanpale *et al.*, 2014). Morphometric variation between stocks of fishes can provide basis for stock structure and may be applicable for studying short time environmentally induced

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variations geared towards successful fisheries management (Murta, 2002, Pinheiro *et al.*, 2005). Morphometrics and meristic characters variations are known to be influenced by both genetic and environmental factors (Dynes *et al.*, 1999). Information on the morphometric and meristic traits of various fins of fishes are used in the determination of sex, species identification and the confirmation or the species suitability for aquaculture activities (Tantarpale, 2014). Previous reports in identification of strain through morphology of *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Tilapia zillii* are based on the total length of the body with measurement of entire body indices. In this present investigation, morphometric and meristic traits study of the fin and fin rays numbers are compared to further report differences between *O. niloticus* and *T. zillii* and other species of the same genus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Samples of the freshwater fish, *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Tilapia zillii* (n=116 and 24 for *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Tilapia zillii* respectively) were bought between April and October 2015 from local fisherman at the bank of Ureje dam, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. Ado-Ekiti, State capital in Nigeria is located on Latitude 07° 40'N Longitude 05° 15' N. The fish were immediately transferred to the Postgraduate Laboratory of the Dept. of Zoology, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti. The fish were sorted into sexes of each species and kept in labeled plastic tanks with continuous aeration.

Morphometric and meristics study of fins was done by the measurements of the fish total length, body weight, different fin lengths and counting the fin rays numbers. The relationship of the fin length variables with the total length of *O. niloticus* and *T. zillii* were determined. Regression analyses were used for the data collected on the fish samples

RESULTS

Total number of 116 and 24 specimens of females and males *O. niloticus* and *T. zillii* were examined and analyzed. Table 1 shows the morphometric characteristics and meristic traits of various fins of *O. niloticus* and *T. zillii*. The fin rays of both species are fairly constant which require no further analysis.

Table1: Mean and standard error of morphometric traits and meristic counts of females and males *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Tilapia zillii* from Ureje dam Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

	<i>O. niloticus</i>	<i>T. zillii</i>	<i>O. niloticus</i>	<i>T. zillii</i>
	Female MEAN±SE	Female MEAN±SE	Male MEAN±SE	Female MEAN±SE
TL (cm)	20.1± 0.14	21.15 ± 0.32	20.17 ± 0.25	20.42 ± 0.62
BW (g)	164.7 ± 2.80	167.8 ± 7.57	170.2 ± 6.02	162.2 ± 11.8
CPD	3.47 ± 0.86	3.41 ± 0.59	3.20 ± 0.49	3.41 ± 0.50
PCFL (cm)	2.62 ± 0.30	2.47 ± 0.37	2.59 ± 0.38	2.61 ± 0.35
PEFL (cm)	1.52 ± 0.42	1.62 ± 0.26	2.05 ± 0.25	1.71 ± 0.54
DFR	27.0 ± 0.12	27.1 ± 0.54	27.0 ± 0.12	26.22 ± 0.78
AFR	12.0 ± 0.15	12.0 ± 0.29	12.0 ± 0.31	12.0 ± 0.45
PCFR	76.0 ± 0.12	7.0 ± 0.35	6.07 ± 0.05	7.3 ± 0.55
PEFR	11.2 ± 0.14	11.0 ± 0.39	12.0 ± 0.18	11.0 ± 0.58
CFR	16.0 ± 0.17	16.0 ± 0.34	16.0 ± 0.44	16.0 ± 0.63
SDF	1.87 ± 0.04	1.93 ± 0.11	1.96 ± 0.65	1.80 ± 0.15
SPEF	2.16 ± 0.03	2.34 ± 0.42	1.98 ± 0.07	2.06 ± 0.13

TL= Total length, WT= weight of the body, CPD= caudal peduncle depth, PCFL= pectoral fin length, PEFL= pelvic fin length, DFR= dorsal fin rays, AFR= anal fin rays, PCFR=pectoral fin rays, PEFR= pelvic fin rays, CFR= caudal fin rays, SDF= length of spine of dorsal fin, SPEF= length of the spine of spine of pectoral fin

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Table2. Relationship between the total length and different fin length and rays of females and males *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Tilapia zillii*

<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i> female	Fins	Fin length	Fin rays	r ²	r
	Dorsal fin	y=0.976+0.044x	Y= 24.6+0.117x		
	Anal fin	y=0.368+ 0.081x	Y=12.09+0.045x	0.002	0.045
	Pelvic fin	Y=1.400+0.043x	Y=5.645+0.052x	0.002	0.045
	Pectoral fin	Y=1.716+0.022x	Y=11.77-0.035x	0.000	0.000
	Caudal fin		Y=15.66+0.002x	5E-06	0.000
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i> male	Fins	Fin length	Fin rays		
	Dorsal fin	Y=0.600+0.065x	Y=25.50+0.072x		
	Anal fin	y= 1.186+0.039x	Y=7.167+0.219x	0.031	0.56
	Pelvic fin	Y=2.867-0.045x	Y=9.182+0.118x	0.102	0.32
	Pectoral fin	Y=1.186+0.039x	Y=9.182+0.118x	0.027	0.16
	Caudal fin		Y=14.48+0.104x	0.003	0.05
<i>Tilapia zillii</i> female	Fins	Fin length	Fin rays		
	Dorsal fin	Y=2.054-0.006x	y = 17.31+0.461x		
	Anal fin	y= 0.065+0.086x	Y=5.635+0.294x	0.104	0.32
	Pelvic fin	Y=0.615+0.081x	Y=11.73-0.025x	0.000	0.00
	Pectoral fin	Y=1.232+0.169x	Y=8.303-0.080x	0.006	0.07
	Caudal fin		Y=18.16-0.127x	0.014	0.037
<i>Tilapia zillii</i> male	Fins	Fin length	Fin rays		
	Dorsal fin	Y=0.882+0.131x	y = 10.94+0.748x		
	Anal fin	y= 0.967+0.052x	Y=5.748+0.262x	0.126	0.35
	Pelvic fin	Y=2.342-0.002x	Y=2.847+0.3847x	0.167	0.41
	Pectoral fin	Y=2.691-0.031x	Y=17.99-0.521x	0.338	0.58
	Caudal fin		Y=7.981+0.436x	0.18	0.42

Morphometrically, the mean total length (cm) of the fish are 20.1 ± 0.14 , 210.15 ± 0.32 and 20.17 ± 0.25 , 20.42 ± 0.62 for female and male of *O. niloticus* and *T. zillii* respectively and the relationship between the various fin length and fin rays is assumed to be Y. The Y value showed positive correlation with the total length (x) using regression formula ($Y=a+bx$) in the two species, whereas the value of a and b for various Y are given in Table 2.

The coefficient of correlation (r) of the total length with fin length which ranged from 0.00 to 0.58 does not show any substantial correlation.

DISCUSSION

Tilapias are suitable for various aquaculture systems due to their ease of propagation, tolerance to handling, fast growth on both natural and manufactured feeds. Tolerance of a wide range of environmental conditions, and high palatability, marketability and nutrient content (Teichert Coddington *et al* (1997).

Morphometric analysis of an organism which is the quantitative analysis of form in terms of size and shape is useful in analyzing their fossil record, the impact of mutations on their shape, developmental changes in form, covariance between ecological factors and shape, as well as for estimating quantitative genetic parameters of shape. (Carpenter *et al.*, 1996)

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Reports on the relationship between body weight and total length of animals have confirmed that one is function of the other. In this study, there is relationship between the body weight and their length of the two *Tilapia species* which confirmed what other Authors have reported on *Cichlids*. The growth of fish in terms of length may not correlate with the body appendages (fins) as observed in this work. The result recorded on the growth and development of Tilapia total length and fin rays showed that there was no correlation between the fin length and the fin rays in both *O. niloticus* and *T. zillii*. The fairly constant numbers of the fin rays observed in this work in both *O. niloticus* and *T. zillii* agreed with the reports of Reed *et al.* (1967), Holden and Reed (1972), Omoniyi and Agbon (2008) that fin rays of the tribe *Tilapiini* do not vary much. Huet (1949) reported variations in study on fin rays of salt water and freshwater races of sticklebacks while Ikusemiju (1975) observed differences in gill raker count of *Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus*. Fins are known to perform various functions based on the mode of life of different fish species. Usha (2000) observed that the anal, caudal, pectoral and pelvic fin of *Catla catla* were longer than that of *Caprinus carpio*, *Labeo rohita* and *Clarias gariepinus* due to its surface feeding habit suited ecologically on vegetation. Both *Catla catla*, *Labeo rohita* and *C. gariepinus* are benthic species and have robust bodies and large pectoral fins which allow them to withstand current on smaller and smoother substratum. Dynes *et al.* (1999) reported that the dorsal and pectoral fin length of pelagic fish, Brooke chart (*Salvelius fontinalis*) were shorter than the littoral species.

It was observed by Lagler, (1962), Usha and Prakasam,(2005) that the increase in size of the fins is usually followed by branching and segmentation of the fin rays. The sequential development of the pectoral fin followed by caudal and dorsal fins appeared to be related to the timely uses of the fins as reported by Whitehead (1975) and Devenport (1995).

The factors affecting the size and shape of the fins and fin ray numbers could be hereditary or environmentally induced. Ikusemiju (1975) reported that the differences in gill raker counts of *Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus* might have occurred as a result of the isolation caused by differences in salinity gradients between two locations where the samples were collected (Lagos and Lekki) in Nigeria. Other environmental factors influencing the shape, size and the number of fin rays in fishes include the nature of substratum in the river or dam, temperature fluctuations, mode of feeding, variation in dietary materials, current of the stream, and ecological factors such as predation.

The objective of any racial study is to establish, with degree of confidence, the proper identification of a fish species in different water bodies. This is due to the fact that many morphometric characteristics and meristic traits still remain dependable tools to categorize fish species especially on the field and they are sensitive to any environmental changes (Fryer and Iles, 1972). In this present study, analysis of morphology and meristic counts of fins of *O. niloticus* and *T. zillii* showed that the two species have similar fins with respect to length and ray numbers. It is therefore suggested that the two species be subjected to further biochemical analysis to further confirm their taxonomic characteristics and genetic purity.

CONCLUSION

O.niloticus and *T.zillii* which are popular candidates for aquacultural practices in Africa and Nigeria in particular collected from Ureje dam; Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria shared similar morphological characteristics and meristic traits. It is therefore suggested that the two species should be investigated by biochemical analysis to further confirm their taxonomic characteristics and their hereditary status.

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